

The history of lifelong education in Spain and other Spanish speaking countries: 1730-1959

Elena Tuparevska

Faculty of Psychology and Education, University of Deusto, Bilbao, Spain

Correspondence: Faculty of Psychology and Education, University of Deusto.

elena.tuparevska3@deusto.es.

This is the Accepted Manuscript of the article. The Version of Record of this manuscript

has been published and is available in International Journal of Lifelong

Education, 41(2), 2022, available online:

<https://doi.org/10.1080/02601370.2022.2047115>

The history of lifelong education in Spain and other Spanish speaking countries: 1730-1959

While the idea of lifelong education in Spain is much older, the history of the concept begins in the 1960s. As digital libraries are becoming a source of new data for researchers, the aim of this study is to examine the history of the terms related to lifelong education and learning in Spain and other Spanish speaking countries by using data published before 1960 and available in Massive Digital Libraries such as Google Books and HathiTrust. The analysis of books and different kinds of texts and discourses published in Spanish from 1400 until 1959 revealed three formative periods in the development of lifelong education that begin in 18th-century Spain during the Enlightenment and spread to Latin America by the mid-19th century where most of the activity is focused in the following century. What emerges are different conceptualisations of permanent education shaped by the social, political, and economic context as well as influential philosophical movements such as Krausism and positivism, on one hand, and by a variety of actors on the other hand.

Keywords: lifelong education; permanent education; Google Books; HathiTrust; Spain; Latin America; history

Introduction

A few scholars have traced the idea of lifelong learning back to ancient times: ancient India (Mandal, 2019), ancient China and the work of Confucius (Aspin et al., 2012), as well as ancient Greece (Matheson & Matheson, 1996). Another historical moment highlighted as crucial in the development of the idea of education as a lifelong process was the work of 17th-century thinkers and pedagogues such as Jan Amos Comenius (Suchodolski, 1979). In the 18th and 19th centuries, it was Condorcet's Report (Hake, 1999), the rise of adult education with the advent of the industrial revolution (Kallen, 1996), and Grundtvig's folk high schools (Špolar & Holford, 2014) that helped promote the idea.

Unlike the idea of lifelong learning, the concept itself has a much shorter history. The first appearances of the concept are traced back to the aftermath of World War I in the UK and US (Field, 2001; Wilson, 2009), usually linked to issues such as the workers' movement and women's suffrage. The 1919 Report of the Ministry of Reconstruction (Field, 2001; Jarvis, 2014) and the works of Basil Yeaxlee in the UK and those of Eduard Lindeman in the US (Centeno, 2011) are usually referred to as the first texts on lifelong education. Nevertheless, it is generally accepted that the concept surfaced on the international agenda in the second half of the 20th century under the influence of international organisations (Tuijnman & Boström, 2002).

However, recent studies on the history of lifelong learning and education in the US and UK using Google Books Search have traced the first uses of the term to 1839 (Ignatovich, 2020), much earlier than previously indicated in the literature. In Spain, the primary education inspectors Avendaño and Cardera in their book *Curso Elemental de Pedagogía* [*Elementary Pedagogy Course*] taught in teacher colleges to future teachers argued in 1850 that 'education includes everything that refers to man's existence...It begins with life, and the whole of life must be devoted to it' (p. 15, author's translation), revealing that the idea of learning across the lifespan was probably well established in 19th-century Spain. Nevertheless, the history of the concept usually begins in the 1960s. As digital libraries are becoming a source of new data for researchers, the aim of this study is to examine the history of the terms regarding lifelong learning in Spain and other Spanish speaking countries by using data published before 1960 and available in Massive Digital Libraries.

Permanent education in Spain

What is known as lifelong education in the UK and US, *éducation permanente* in France, *lebenslange erziehung* or *lebenslanges lernen* in Germany, is often called *educación permanente* in Spain (Limón Mendizabal, 1988). For example, the Spanish version of the Faure report *Aprender a Ser* (Faure et al., 1973) translated the term lifelong education with *educación permanente*, and as recently as 2018, the *Proposal for a Council Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning* was translated as *Propuesta de Recomendación del Consejo Relativa a las Competencias Clave Para el Aprendizaje Permanente*.

Regarding the history of permanent education in Spain, Limón Mendizabal (1988) traced back the idea of the need for human beings to learn throughout their lives to the 1599 *Official Plan for Jesuit Education (Ratio Studiorum)*. Next, the idea emerged during the Age of the Enlightenment in an anonymous utopian Spanish work that talked about the need to provide education from childhood to old age (Limón Mendizabal, 1988). During that same era, Fernández (2000) credited the work of Spanish education reformers with spreading the idea across the country. In the 18th century, a handful of intellectuals, one of them Gaspar Melchor de Jovellanos, inspired by the Enlightenment that was already sweeping through other European countries, launched a crusade in favour of modern thought and science, and in the service of economic, technological, and social development (Fernández, 2000). In the period between the 18th and 19th centuries, Spanish reformers like Jovellanos regarded education as a continuous process and assumed that there was a continuum between education, life, and society, and the Royal Asturian Institute of Nautics and Mineralogy established at the end of the 18th century became the embodiment of this new educational paradigm (Fernández, 2000).

These ideas continued into the 19th century. Thus, the Junta of the public teaching reform in 1813 defined education as a process that must ‘embrace the whole system of human knowledge and ensure that men in all stages of life can easily preserve their knowledge or acquire new knowledge’ (de Navas et al., 1813, author’s translation). The 19th century also gave rise to adult education, another occurrence credited with keeping the idea of lifelong education alive (Medina Ferrer et al., 2013). After the adoption of the *Moyano Act* in 1857 and the introduction of night lessons, republicans, anarchists and socialists were the first to focus on adult education by establishing workers' centres, educational clubs or *ateneos*, and other similar institutions throughout Spain (Tiana Ferrer, 1992). The Free Institution of Education that emerged in 1876 played a key role in the development of these ideas as it gave rise to important permanent education initiatives such as the Association for Women’s Education, as well as university extensions and popular universities (Flecha, 1990).

The history of the concept, on the other hand, is much more recent with scholars tracing it back to the late 1960s (García Redondo, 2017) and usually crediting international organisations such as UNESCO with its introduction (Gomes & Lucio-Villegas, 2009; Paz Fernández, 1984). A White Paper titled *La Educación en España. Bases Para Una Política Educativa* [*The Education in Spain. The Basis for Educational Policy*] from 1969 is referenced as one of the first texts to introduce the concept. The White Paper (1969) advocated for an education understood ‘as a permanent process throughout the life course of a man, that should continue after completing one’s studies within the formal educational system’ (p. 95, author’s translation). The White Paper is considered as a prelude to the *Law on Education and Financing the Educational Reform* [*Ley General de Educación y Financiamiento de la Reforma Educativa*]. When the law was adopted in 1970, it aimed to reform the current

educational system within a permanent education framework (Limón Mendizabal, 1988).

Massive Digital Libraries

Together with the Internet Archive and the Open Library, Google Books and HathiTrust are what Weiss and James (2013) call Massive Digital Libraries or extremely large digital collections that hold over a million digitised print book content amassed from multiple digitization projects. Massive Digital Libraries have been used recently to discover the origins of terms and related concepts across different academic subjects, to verify facts and confirm claims about the history of coinage and conception (Sutton & Griffiths, 2018). They have also been used to examine the history of the terms lifelong learning and education (Ignatovich, 2020).

With its collection of more than 30 million books and a catalogue comparable to other major research libraries (Jones, 2010), Google Books offers researchers access to new data. While English publications are predominant, Google Books has an important Spanish collection. Two key libraries in Spain, the Complutense University of Madrid Library and the National Library of Catalonia joined Google Books. In the US, some of Google Books' main partner libraries have considerable holdings of books in Spanish (Bjørner, 2007; Weiss & James, 2013). HathiTrust which was included to complement the study and to ensure other important publications are not overlooked is the second largest Massive Digital Library after Google Books (Weiss, 2016) and has important holdings of Spanish books as well with Spanish being the fourth most represented language on the platform (HathiTrust, n.d.).

Methodology

This study uses Google Books (<https://books.google.com>) and HathiTrust (<https://www.hathitrust.org/>) searches that allow searching for books and different kinds of public, professional, academic, official, and creative texts and discourses published in Spanish from 1400 until 1959. Several series of queries were run in 2021 for the terms *enseñanza permanente*, *educación permanente*, and *aprendizaje permanente* using the advanced search modes and the search for exact phrase options. The queries were run for the following periods: 1400 to 1500, 1500 to 1600, 1600 to 1700, 1700 to 1800, 1800 to 1900, and 1900 to 1959. After removing duplicates and documents with wrong metadata, a total of 226 documents were selected for analysis. The selected documents included: texts available in full view (35), snippet view (190), and preview (1). Out of the 190 snippet view documents I managed to track down 92 in libraries, archives and on the internet. In the end, the corpus for analysis included 127 full-view, 98 snippet-view texts, and 1 preview. Texts in limited (search-only) mode on HathiTrust were excluded, as well as texts with no preview in both libraries. If the date of publication could not be verified, texts of multivolume works available only in snippet view were also excluded.

Most of the documents were published in Spain (57) and Latin America (163) (Table 1). The majority were published in the 20th century. The types of texts found were very heterogeneous and ranged from books, magazine and journal articles, minutes, judicial documents, decrees, gazettes, art publications, newsletters, proceedings from congress, annals, reports, philosophical treatises, biographies, bulletins, addresses, novels, and other texts. Once the data was selected, the next step was collecting bibliographic information for all of the works including title, author, publisher, country, and publication date. I then proceeded with coding the material and identifying the main themes and the meaning of the terms in the text. The themes were

developed inductively. This involved an in-depth and systematic reading and rereading of the data in order to identify emerging themes. I made notes and headings in the text as I read. I then transcribed my notes onto a table. Themes were repeatedly reviewed and classified. One of the advantages of inductive analysis is its flexibility allowing researchers to analyse a variety of texts. Moreover, unlike other approaches, it does not allow for key themes to be obscured by the overemphasis of well-established methodologies (Thomas, 2006). However, inductive analysis is a time-consuming process. Furthermore, its flexibility can result in inconsistencies in the analysis. Deciding what aspects of the data to focus on can also be challenging.

[Table 1 near here]

Results

Permanent education in Spain

The 18th century and the emergence of permanent education

The earliest occurrence of permanent education (*enseñanza permanente*) was found in the 18th century, coinciding with the advent of the Age of Enlightenment in Spain. A work from 1730 titled *Memorias Historicas de la Fundación, y Progressos de la Insigne Universidad de Valencia* [*Historical Memoirs of the Foundation, and Progress of the Illustrious University of Valencia*] written by Francisco Ortí y Figuerola talked about the benefits of permanent education, used in a literal sense in reference to the foundation of the University of Valencia. At the time, Valencia was one of the most important centres of *novatores* activity. The so-called *novatores* were the forerunners of the Enlightenment in the 17th and the beginning of the 18th century and they promoted social and scientific renewal. Furthermore, Valencia was the birthplace of Gregorio Mayans y Siscar, one of the most important representatives of the early Enlightenment

in Spain. Not only did Mayans study and later taught at the University of Valencia but in his work *Carta al Pavorde Calatayud* [*Letter to the Provost Calatayud*] (1760) he revealed that *Francisco Ortí*, the rector of the university, had written the *Historical Memoirs* with the help of many and especially with the help of Mayans himself.

In that same century, only one more reference was found, also connected to the Enlightenment. It is a text published at the end of the century about the establishment of the Royal Asturian Institute by Antonio Valdes (*Noticia del Real Instituto Asturiano* [*News from the Royal Asturian Institute*], 1795) that uses the term for professional training and development in mineralogy with the aim of promoting and advancing the stone coal trade. The Royal Asturian Institute, a technical school of nautical and mineralogy studies, was established by Gaspar Melchor de Jovellanos, one of the most important figures of the Age of Enlightenment in Spain who wrote the first systematic treatise on education of that era. The results of this study support the argument by Fernández (2000) that the idea of permanent education goes back to the 18th- and 19th-century work of Spanish education reformers such as Jovellanos and that the Royal Asturian Institute became the hallmark of the new educational paradigm. In *Noticia del Real Instituto Asturiano* we find two instances of permanent education, one of them in a letter from Valdes to Jovellanos. However, posthumous publications of Jovellanos' works (*Jovellanos: Nuevos Datos Para su Biografía* [*Jovellanos: New Data for His Biography*], 1885) reveal that Jovellanos was not only familiar with the term but used it himself in a letter probably written to Antonio Ponz, another Enlightenment era figure who, incidentally, was educated at the University of Valencia. In that same letter, Jovellanos made a reference to a work by Mayans.

While in the 16th and 17th centuries the Protestant Reformation ushered in adult and permanent education activities in Northern and Central Europe, the Counter

Reformation of the Catholic part of Southern Europe opposed literacy for the general public and instead focused on visual imagery (Hake, 2011). It is the Enlightenment movement in the 18th century that laid the ground for the rise of permanent education in Spain understood as professional training and development, on the one hand, and in a literal sense as long-term education or courses given on a permanent basis, on the other hand.

The 19th century and Krausism

Permanent education was absent for most of the first half of the 19th century. One possible explanation for this discontinuity is the fact that this was a turbulent time in Spanish history marked by the invasion of Napoleon's troops, the Independence War, the loss of the colonies, the Carlist wars, uprisings, and frequent changes in the political system. Furthermore, Spain was plagued by hardship and poverty. This was a century of bad harvests, followed by famine, the most severe ones the famines of 1803 and 1804. The first references appeared in 1845. Until the 1860s, these were mostly translations of foreign authors or republications of works from the previous century. For example, we find *Noticia del Real Instituto Asturiano* republished in a work from 1859 (*Obras Publicadas e Inéditas de Don Gaspar Melchor de Jovellanos [Published and Unedited Works by Don Gaspar Melchor de Jovellanos]*).

Among the translations, a particularly important work was *Ideal de la Humanidad Para la Vida* (1860) on Karl Christian Friedrich Krause's philosophy. Krausism was introduced in Spain by Julián Sanz del Río in several of his works, among them *Ideal de la Humanidad Para la Vida*. Based on philosophical idealism, Krausism embraced humanism, ethics, and secularism, and attempted to reconcile monotheism and pantheism, philosophy and religion. It soon became a profoundly

influential liberal school of thought that left a trace in most spheres of society including education, not only in Spain but the entire Spanish speaking world. The analysis showed the influence Krausism had also on shaping the conceptualisation of permanent education in the 19th and 20th centuries. In 1864, permanent education was used in a work by Emilio Castelar (*Cartas a un Obispo Sobre la Libertad de la Iglesia* [*Letters to a Bishop on the Freedom of the Church*]), an influential Spanish writer and statesman who was a student of Sanz del Río and a Krausist. In fact, in the same paragraph where Castelar used it in a citation by Lessing, he also cited Krause who maintained that man's relationship with God 'is likeness to God, knowledge of God, Union with God, manifesting itself in the intelligence, in the feeling, in the will, in the whole life' (p. 180-181). The following year, we find *Cartas a un Obispo Sobre la Libertad de la Iglesia* reproduced as a clarification and a summary of Castelar's ideas in his work *La Civilización en los Cinco Primeros Siglos del Cristianismo* [*Civilization in the First Five Centuries of Christianity*], and in 1876 we find it in a republication. Furthermore, in 1886, we encounter permanent education in another one of his works (*Galeria Historica de Mujeres Celebres* [*Historical Gallery of Famous Women*]). Around this time, permanent education also appeared in an article by the journalist and academic Francisco María Tubino (1878) in the weekly paper *La Academia*. Although Tubino would later abandon Krausism, in his earlier years he was influenced by Krause, especially in his philosophical and social studies (Tubino, 1989).

The works from this century continued conceptualising permanent education as professional training and development. They also introduced permanent education as professional training and development in reference to two new fields, etymology and the graphic forms of art. Moreover, they introduced new conceptualisations. It was in the 19th century that permanent education first appeared in a religious connotation

where religion was depicted as ‘permanent education of the human race’ (Castelar, 1864, p. 13, author’s translation). Other conceptualisations included permanent education personified as a well-known, historical figure or history.

The 20th century and international organisations

The influence of Krausism seemed to continue into the early 20th century. Out of the two works found from the 1900s, one was a republication of *Ideal de la Humanidad Para la Vida* from 1904. In the following decade, permanent education appeared in an article by Adrenio (1918) in the illustrated magazine *Nuevo Mundo*. Adrenio was the pseudonym of Eduardo Gómez de Baquero, who was a student of Francisco Giner de los Ríos and was well acquainted with the work of Krause. Giner was a student of Julián Sanz del Río himself. He came onto the scene at a time when there were very few permanent education initiatives and they were mostly religious and private endeavours (Limón Mendizabal, 1988). In 1876, influenced by Sanz del Río’s teachings and Krausism, Giner established the Free Institution of Education, one of the most important educational institutions of the era. Moreover, Giner and his Free Institution of Education played a key role in the dissemination of Krause’s philosophy in both Spain and Latin America. In 1920, it was the institution’s journal, the *Bulletin of the Free Institution of Education*, that introduced a new meaning of permanent education. In the section dedicated to discussing research from Europe and America, the term was used in a summary of an article published two years earlier in the *Journal of Educational Psychology*. The article in question by Wiley (1918) was an experimental study on the three methods of teaching high school students - lecturing, textbooks and laboratory - that used the term of permanent learning in the sense of permanent retention of the facts imparted in a lesson. This new conceptualisation did not seem to catch on.

Nevertheless, we find earlier conceptualisations of permanent education in works of authors with links to Giner and the Free Institution of Education. For example, Ramón Pérez de Ayala (1952) writing about his teacher and later friend Leopoldo Alas, Clarín, claimed that ‘all his works contain a permanent education’ (p. 9). Ayala was Clarín’s student at the University of Oviedo where he came in close contact with Krausism, and his teacher, the Spanish writer Clarín, was a student of Giner, whom he called a dearest teacher and spiritual father (Lissorgues, 1996). The two remained close friends throughout their lives and although it is difficult to define Clarín as a Krausist, the impact Krausism had on him in his formative years seems to have had a lasting effect (Kronik, 1981). Apart from the life of a historic or well-known figure as permanent education, the idea of history as permanent education was another conceptualisation linked with Giner. The idea appeared in an article by the writer Miguel de Unamuno titled *Cartas al Amigo* [*Letters to the Friend*] addressed to José Ortega y Gasset, originally published in 1933 in the daily newspaper *Ahora*. Both Unamuno and Gasset were connected to the Free Institution of Education. Although Unamuno could by no means be called a Krausist, not only had he read Krause but in his youth, he was Giner’s student and an admirer of his work (Molleda, 1976). Although their relationship would later sour, Giner’s interest in Unamuno awoke when he came across Unamuno’s work *Ensayos* [*Essays*] which stressed the civilizing and beneficial effect of Krausism on Spain, and the two corresponded for a while (Molleda, 1976).

Furthermore, apart from new editions of Krause’s work, we see that a new edition of Castelar’s *La Civilización en los Cinco Primeros Siglos del Cristianismo* came out in 1947. However, these were not the only ideas from previous centuries still circulating around. The unedited works of Jovellanos were collected and reprinted in

1913, 1931, 1947, and 1956, making sure that the ideas of the Enlightenment did not disappear but continued influencing new generations of Spanish writers and thinkers.

The conceptualisation of permanent education for professional training and development introduced in the 18th century by Jovellanos continued into the next one. In the article *Criminalidad y Represión* [*Criminality and Repression*], Prins (1911) discussed permanent education of ‘a workshop where even the nuances of the trade are learned experimentally and only by daily contact with a more skilled colleague’ (p. 77) in reference to introducing professional training in prisons to teach inmates a trade and to enable them to make a living once they leave. Other references were related to military culture, agriculture and the optimal use of ploughs, medicine and training of doctors, as well as training of mothers in childcare and preventable diseases as a way of tackling child mortality (Curbelo, 1953). Around this time, the idea of permanent education in a literal sense entered official documents and educational policies with several documents depicting permanent education as permanent professorship by a tenured professor (Gaceta de Madrid, 1918).

The early 20th century marked another discontinuity in the shaping of permanent education in Spain. In the second half of the 19th century, it had spread to Latin America, and by the 20th century more and more of the works referring to permanent education were published in Latin America. In comparison, Spain’s contributions diminished significantly, especially until the 1950s. The Restoration period with its constant changes of governments, internal crisis, and instability, Primo de Rivera’s dictatorship, the Spanish Civil War, and the repression, political purges, and economic hardship of the first decade of Franco’s dictatorship did not allow these ideas to thrive.

However, this changed in the late 1950s. It was also around this time that a new conceptualisation emerged under the influence of international conferences and international organisations. One such conference was the International Congress on Popular Education held in Charleroi, Belgium, where Spain participated together with the rest of the European nations. An article titled *La Educación Permanente* [*Permanent Education*] (1958) written by the Spanish delegate at the conference, Luis Moreno Manglano, revealed that one of the main conclusions of the congress was that research into permanent education would have to play an important part at the International Conference on Adult Education which was to be organised by UNESCO in 1960.

It was not only UNESCO that was shaping this new conceptualisation. The International Bureau of Education (IBE) founded in Geneva in the 1920s and at the time not yet part of UNESCO helped organise the XXIst International Conference on Public Education in Geneva whose Recommendation No. 47 concerning facilities for education in rural areas argued for the introduction of a system of permanent education in the more developed regions with the aim of providing vocational information and better training for all adults, advancing general culture and offering ‘a deeper knowledge of the key problems of the modern world’ (*Revista de Educación*, 1959, p. 17, author’s translation). The following year, the recommendation appeared in two Spanish scientific journals, *Revista de Educación* and *Revista Española de Pedagogía*, most likely in an attempt to disseminate the information to school authorities and educators as requested by the conference organisers. Thus, we see that permanent education was present in scientific journals and weekly cultural magazines such as *La Estafeta Literaria* more than a decade before it was introduced in Spanish educational policy in the late 1960s.

However, we do note some confusion around the terminology. While the Spanish version of the recommendation used permanent education, the official English version used *adult education on a continuing basis*. A similar problem occurred at the 1958 International Congress on Popular Education where popular education, adult education, and further training were used as synonyms (David, 1962). Manglano (1958) himself used permanent education as a synonym for popular education. Furthermore, Adolfo Maíllo (1959), a member of the Spanish delegation at the XXI International Conference on Public Education who some years later would publish a book titled *Educación de Adultos. Educación Permanente* [*Adult Education. Permanent Education*] defined permanent education as a broadening of the concept of post-school education in another issue of *Revista de Educación*. In any case, permanent education was already generating debate as can be appreciated from Manglano's (1958) words: 'we were dealing with vague issues, beautiful words and ideals... that would easily be destroyed in the face of the day-to-day realities in countries where individuals were motivated by commercial and professional interests' (p. 11, author's translation).

Permanent education in Latin America

The mid-19th century and the nature of permanent education

In the second half of the 19th century, permanent education had spread to Latin America. By this time, many parts of Latin America had won their independence. In 1852, the term appeared in a publication from Mexico. It was the same work by Niels Nikolaus Falck *Prolegómenos del Derecho: Enciclopedia Jurídica* that was published in Spain a few years before. In the following decades of the 19th century, the term spread to Chile, Peru, Argentina, Cuba, Uruguay, Venezuela, and Ecuador. During this century, we find the same conceptualisations that had already emerged in Spain: permanent

education in a religious connotation, permanent education in a literal sense, the life of historical figures as permanent education, and history as permanent education. For example, there was a reference to the work and doctrines of the Uruguayan writer and politician José Pedro Varela as ‘permanent education and as indisputable glory to the homeland’ (Herrero y Espinosa, 1885, p. 195, author’s translation). What was new, however, was the appearance of permanent education as professional training and development closely connected to the lower social classes. A text from Chile (*Estudios Sobre la Colonización i Emigración Europea a Chile [A Study on Colonisation and European Emigration to Chile]*, 1867) referred to ‘permanent education of the lower classes of our society’ to enable them to compete with European workers (p. 152, author’s translation). In Argentina, *La Fundicion Argentina: Demanda Contra la Provincia de Buenos Aires [Fundicion Argentina: Lawsuit Against the Province of Buenos Aires]* (1881) stated that ‘the permanent education of a number of children, offered this society vigorous soldiers of labour and work’ (p. 14, author’s translation) connecting the idea of permanent education to industrial progress as well as education and training of children for labour. These results reveal that the history of permanent education was not always an unproblematic narrative but was also about ‘the uncomfortable and inconvenient reminders of the past’ (Hake, 2011, p. 18). Child labour constitutes one such unremembered and inconvenient historical fact. For example, in the early 20th century, half of the child population in Colombia was out of school, living in poverty, and needed to contribute to their family’s income, and legislators and intellectuals defended manual labour for children as an important factor in the physical and psychological development of the child and as mental hygiene (Hurtado, 2017). This was not only a Latin American reality. In his often-cited book *The Meaning of Adult Education*, Lindeman (1926) revealed the realities of the 19th and

20th centuries and child labour as he himself ‘had already earned [his] way in the world from the age of nine, had learned the ship-building trade’ (pp. xiv-xv).

The 19th century in Latin America saw also the first example of a deeper engagement with the meaning and nature of permanent education, and this idea was closely connected to another philosophical theory, positivism. In 1892, Valentín Letelier, an intellectual, educator, and later rector of the University of Chile, published *Filosofía de la Educación* [*Philosophy of Education*]. Letelier was influenced by positivist philosophy and this was reflected in his work. Formulated by the French philosopher Auguste Comte, positivism built on ideas from the Enlightenment such as the light of reason and embraced the scientific method and the data of experience. It soon became an influential philosophy and spread to Latin America. In Uruguay, for example, José Pedro Varela influenced by positivism in his travels to Europe and particularly the US overhauled his country’s educational system. In Spain, positivism influenced Krausism and gave rise to a new strand sometimes referred to as Krausopositivism. Positivism has been linked to Freemasonry, one of the main but underreported shaping forces of popular education in Catholic countries and a vehicle for social and political reform (Steele, 2010). Unlike the conservatism of British Freemasonry, Freemasons in Southern Europe were a radical and anticlerical force that helped spread the ideals of the Enlightenment in opposition to the Catholic Church (Steele, 2010). Letelier himself was a Freemason, and so were Krause, Castelar, Lessing whom Castelar cited in reference to permanent education, Francisco María Tubino, as well as persons close to the Free Institution of Education, pointing at a possible link between Freemasonry and the development of permanent education in the Spanish speaking world of the 19th century.

Letelier's book argued that 'this permanent education we are subjected to' does not only come from society, but nature and the environment play important roles too (p. 34). Letelier highlighted three instruments of human education: school, society, and nature where 'everything in the universe is school, and everyone in life is a teacher', and 'life, in one word, is a perpetual education and a perpetual learning' (p. 38-39, author's translation). According to Letelier, the most complete education was one that embraced the whole life of man.

Letelier's work was influential both at home and abroad. *Filosofía de Educación* influenced a generation of Chilean educators such as Dario E. Salas, Luis Galdames, and Pedro Aguirre Cerda (Jobet, 1957). Dario Salas who would spend time in the US and meet John Dewey would later write about 'interpreting education as life and not as mere preparation for life' (Jobet, 1957, p. 15). Letelier's work also resonated abroad. For example, it was well known in Spain. The same year it was published in Chile, it also came out in Spain. In 1906, the Spanish sociologist Adolfo Posada not only wrote about *Filosofía de Educación* as a truly complete and systematic treatise on the science of education, but he also added that there were not many works of this kind in Spain (Posada, 1957). Furthermore, Letelier's influence was long-lasting. An issue of *Anales de la Universidad de Chile* from 1957, number 105, was dedicated to his work and legacy. There we find another reference to permanent education by Letelier (1957) but in a literal sense criticising the lack of permanent professorships at the University of London in the late 19th century when it served as an examination centre instead of a teaching university, pointing to the fact that authors were aware of the different meanings of the term.

The 20th century and increased activity

In the early 20th century, we find permanent education as professional training and development still linked with the lower social classes in an article on permanent education in parenthood ‘by means of movable signs on the walls, breastfeeding propaganda, hygiene advice, alcoholism prevention, diffusion of savings’ (Arana, 1918, p. 718). However, this soon changed and we find it referring to a wide range of areas: from agriculture, forestry, medicine, oil industry, water irrigation, music, textiles, to co-ops. In agriculture, a book from 1929 pointed at the necessity of a permanent education for farmers that went beyond agriculture and encompassed managing one’s finances and economizing, as well as family education and female education in order to reinstate traditional roles and values (Campolieti, 1929). A document from the Argentinian Ministry of Agriculture and Commerce (1959) discussed the permanent education of farmers in agriculture for the ‘execution of the necessary cultural and mechanical practices capable of preserving and even improving the soil’ (p. 141). Other references connected to agriculture referred to cocoa cultivation and training in agricultural credit-related activities. In medicine, the uses of permanent education were varied as well ranging from prevention and treatment of infectious diseases such as rabies or tuberculosis, prenatal education, to occupational medicine for workers. By the 1950s, discussions moved to the topic of ‘the accelerated advance of science’ (Institute of Tisiology, 1952, p. 220) driving the need for permanent education for professionals such as doctors and the rising costs of such education.

How was this professional training delivered? The subject of providers emerged during this period. Besides schools, universities, and institutes, libraries and museums were highlighted from the 1920s onwards. For example, a report from the Argentinian National Commission on Culture (1945) referred to the Museum of Theatre as a provider of permanent education for actors and researchers. Other providers included

associations, cooperatives, leagues, and clubs. In music, the establishment of symphonic orchestras provided permanent education. Institutions were not the only way permanent education was delivered. Books, flyers, text, and writing were considered important in providing permanent education, especially for the masses. Illustrated magazines such as *Pluma y Lápiz*, a magazine on literature and art linked to the modernist movement, were regarded as permanent education that ‘educates the artistic taste, exercises a pedagogical mission of beauty, does an honourable and rewarding social work’, as the Chilean poet and professor Bórquez Solar (1927, p. 57) revealed in his memoirs. (Incidentally, Bórquez Solar knew Letelier, as stated in the rest of his memoirs).

The analysis showed that the new nations of the continent were also using permanent education as a tool for nation-building. Joaquín Víctor González (1935) talked about ‘permanent education of the national soul’ (p. 284), and an article titled *Curso Superior de Historia de Colombia* [*Advanced Course on the History of Colombia*] (1949) referred to history courses and the establishment of a public chair within the Colombian Academy of History as permanent education ‘of a harmonious and creative nationalism that explains to the citizens the pride of belonging to the homeland’ (p. 425, author’s translation). The conceptualisations of permanent education in a literal sense and the life of a historic figure as permanent education continued throughout the 20th century.

By this time, permanent education had spread to the rest of Latin America appearing in works published in Colombia, Guatemala, Bolivia, Costa Rica, Honduras, the Dominican Republic, and El Salvador. What characterised this century was the fact that now there were more publications from Latin America than from Spain and the majority of these publications came from Argentina. By the beginning of the 20th century, Argentina had become not only one of the wealthiest countries in Latin

America but in the world, ranking 10th in the world economy. This was a time of prosperity and cosmopolitanism and culture and science were booming. Thus, permanent education appeared in a plethora of medical, political, and law journals, journals on education, political sciences, economic sciences, and philosophy. We also find it in the influential literary magazines *Sur* and *Nosotros*, and the popular sports magazine *El Gráfico*.

However, there were changes on the horizon – with nationalism, populism, and fascism on the rise – not only in Argentina but throughout the continent, and this was echoed in the development of permanent education. Although we find positivists such as José Pedro Varela using permanent education in their works and the principal proponents of Krausism in Latin America such as Yirigoyen and José Martí referenced in the works of other authors in connection to the concept, we find the development of permanent education reflecting the times and linked to the many new movements flourishing in the 20th century. We see the communist party talking about permanent education for the proletariat and one of the most important theoreticians of communism in Uruguay, Arismendi (1953), referring to ‘the ideological work and the work of permanent education of the cadres’ (p. 63). Radicals adopted permanent education in their vocabulary and we find it in magazines such as *Hechos e Ideas: Revista Radical* and works by members of the Radical Civic Union such as Sagarna and del Mazo. Furthermore, we find it in reference to the doctrine of Peronism in the work of Perón (1953) himself as ‘special preparation and training for our leaders’ and ‘preparation of our people’, and even in works of fascists such as, for example, Campolieti who was a sympathiser of Mussolini.

Conclusion

Three formative periods in the history of permanent education and learning in the Spanish speaking world have been distinguished. The first period was associated with the Enlightenment in Spain during the 18th century and the work of individuals such as Mayans and Jovellanos who ushered in new ideas and modernisation, particularly in education, and created the conditions for permanent education as professional training and development and long-term education. From the second half until the end of the 19th century, a second formative period emerged when permanent education spread to the newly independent Latin American countries. Industrialisation, modernisation, and the development of science, on one hand, and, on the other hand, new philosophies and new ways of understanding the world such as Krausism and later positivism were shaping permanent education and the resulting tensions with the Catholic Church and within the individual gave rise to new conceptualisations such as, for example, permanent education in a religious connotation. A third period can be identified in the 20th century. In Spain, this period was characterised by a lot of the same tensions and concerns from the previous century continuing into the new one, and the rising influence of international organisations such as UNESCO and IBE a decade before the concept entered educational policy. In Latin America, the period was characterised by increased engagement with the concept, especially in Argentina, and new concerns such as creating a national identity and a sense of belonging and pride, as well as new movements ranging from radicalism, communism, Peronism, to fascism shaping permanent education and generating greater demand for provision of learning opportunities. This resulted in the development of new providers such as libraries, museums, associations, cooperatives, leagues, clubs, and orchestras, and different delivery methods such as books, flyers, text, writing, and magazines.

As Gomes and Lucio-Villegas (2009) pointed out ‘all concepts are born and defined within historical, social and cultural landscapes’ (p. 71) and this is evident in the three formative periods of permanent education in the Spanish speaking world. Another point that is evident is the variety of actors with different, often conflicting, agendas that helped shape permanent education ranging from educators, academics, writers, intellectuals, scientists, lawmakers, the Church, political parties, to international organisations and the new conceptualisations that emerged as a way of reconciling some of the tensions that arose from the conflicting narratives. Scholars have pointed to the many discontinuities in the history of lifelong learning (Centeno, 2011; Field, 2001), and this is the third point revealed by the analysis and especially evident in Spain during the first halves of the 19th and 20th centuries. Finally, what emerges is not only a narrative full of discontinuities but also, at times, a problematic narrative with its links with the lower social classes and child labour.

Regarding the use of Massive Digital Libraries data, the study points that it can be useful for studying the history of different terms related to lifelong learning and education as it provides rich, new data that can offer new insights as well as revisions of well-established facts. It is especially useful for analysing pre-20th century phenomena as most of the found works (30 out of 32) in the period until 1900 were full-view. However, its use is limited for 20th century works, as only 5 out of 194 were full-view, and needs to be combined with searches in libraries, archives, and the internet.

Wrong metadata and the lack of editing and quality control in the digitization process continue to be a problem. For example, the work *Estudios Sobre la Colonización i Emigración Europea a Chile* [A Study on Colonisation and European Emigration to Chile] was found inside another book titled *Teoria de un Sistema Administrativo y Económico Para la República de Chile* [The Theory of an

Administrative and Economic System for the Republic of Chile] from 1834. Multivolume works such as periodicals and magazines were especially problematic as the date in the metadata and the work's actual date often did not match. Instead of giving the date of the publication of the actual volume in the series, Google Books listed the date when the periodical began publication.

Another issue was duplicates. Duplicates were especially a problem in HathiTrust. HathiTrust Collection Committee (2012) has already acknowledged HathiTrust's problem with duplicates which is primarily due to issues with underlying metadata. However, although its current duplicate detection processes are flawed, the problem is unlikely to be solved in the foreseeable future because removing them would be expensive and fraught with error, and because the duplicates can be valuable to scholars in certain fields (HathiTrust Collection Committee, 2012). However, different editions of the same work (usually published in different years) were included in the analysis as there was a possibility the new edition could include changes and revisions. Issues such as wrong metadata and duplicates make the process of working with Massive Digital Libraries data complicated and lengthy as each entry needs to be checked manually.

Unlike the study by Ignatovich (2020), this study opted not to use Ngram Viewer to map out and visualize the history of the analysed terms. Although Ngram Viewer showed works with the term *educación permanente* in the 19th century, a closer analysis of Google Books revealed that they were not exact matches. Ngram Viewer has already been criticized for the unreliability of its data (Zięba & Mickiewicz, 2018), the oversimplicity of its interface (Davies, 2014), as well as the lack of metadata and context, which seriously limits its potential as a tool for measuring linguistic and socio-cultural changes and trends over time (Zięba & Mickiewicz, 2018). Other

methods for carrying out a search in Google Books such as the Internet Date Detection (IDD) research method (Sutton & Griffiths, 2018) were discarded as well since the search yielded similar results that were not superior to the ones obtained through the advanced search mode in Google Books.

References:

Andrenio. (1918, 13 September). Circulacion. Educación [Circulation. Education].

Nuevo Mundo, 1288.

Arana, A. M. (1918). Protección a la infancia [Protection to Childhood]. *Boletín*

Mensual del Museo Social Argentino, 7, 702–719.

Arismendi, R. (1953). El congreso de los constructores del comunismo; Acerca de la obra de Stalin "Problemas economicos del socialismo en la U.R.S.S." Partido Comunista del Uruguay [The congress of the builders of communism; About Stalin's work "Economic problems of socialism in the U.S.S.R"]. Ediciones Pueblos Unidos. Retrieved from Google Books.

Aspin, D., Evans, K., Chapman, J., & Bagnall, R. (2012). Introduction and

overview. In D. N. Aspin, J. Chapman, K. Evans & R. Bagnall (Eds.),

Second International Handbook of Lifelong Learning (pp. xlv-lxxxiv).

Springer.

Avendaño, J., & Carderera, M. (1850). *Curso elemental de pedagogía*

[*Elementary Pedagogy Course*]. Establecimiento Tipográfico de A.

Vicente.

http://biblioteca.galiciiana.gal/es/catalogo_imagenes/grupo.do?path=100

1291

- Ayala, R. P. (1952). "Clarín" y D. Leopoldo Alas [Clarín and D. Leopoldo Alas]. *Archivum: Revista de la Facultad de Filosofía y Letras*, 2, 5–21.
- Bórquez Solar, A. (1927). Bizarrías de Antaño [Bizarrities of yesteryear]. *Atenea*, 1(1), 56–60.
- Bjørner, S. (2007). Complutense University of Madrid: Different language, similar experience. *Searcher*, 15(4), 22–22.
https://www.infotoday.com/searcher/apr07/Grogg_Ashmore.shtml
- Campolieti, R. (1929). *La organización de la agricultura argentina (Ensayo de política agraria)* [The organization of Argentine agriculture (Essay on agrarian policy)]. Pedro M. Aquino.
- Castelar, E. (1864). *Cartas a un obispo sobre la libertad de la iglesia* [Letters to a bishop on the freedom of the church]. La Democracia.
- Castelar, E. (1865). *La civilización en los cinco primeros siglos del Cristianismo* [Civilization in the first five centuries of Christianity]. Librerías de San Martín.
- Castelar, E. (1886). *Galería histórica de mujeres celebres* [Historical gallery of famous women]. Tipográfico de Alvarez Hermanos.
- Centeno, V. (2011). Lifelong learning: A policy concept with a long past but a short history. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 30(2), 133-150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02601370.2010.547616>
- Curbelo, A. A. (1953). La mortalidad post neonatal en España [Postnatal mortality in Spain]. *Revista Internacional de Sociología*, 43, 105–121.
- David, M. (1962). *Adult education in Yugoslavia*. UNESCO.

- Davies, M. (2014). Making Google Books n-grams useful for a wide range of research on language change. *International Journal of Corpus Linguistics*, 19(3), 401–416. <https://doi.org/10.1075/ijcl.19.3.04dav>
- de Navas, M. G., Vargas y Ponce, J., Tapia, E., Clemencín, D., de la Cuadra, R., & Quintana, M. J. (1813). *Informe de la Junta creada por la regencia para proponer los medios de proceder al arreglo de los diversos ramos de instrucción pública*.
http://www.cervantesvirtual.com/obra-visor/informe-de-la-junta-creada-por-la-regencia--0/html/ff034002-82b1-11df-acc7-002185ce6064_2.html
- E. O. R. (1949). Curso superior de historia de Colombia [*Advanced Course on the History of Colombia*]. *Revista de Historia de América*, 28, 425–426. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20137867>
- Faure, E., Herrera, F., Kaddoura, A. R., Lopes, H., Petrovski, A. V., Rahnama, M., & Ward, F. C. (1973). *Aprender a ser: La educación del futuro* [*Learning to be: The world of education today and tomorrow*]. UNESCO.
- Fernández, J. A. (2000). El descubrimiento de la educación permanente [The re-discovery of the continuing education]. *Educación XXI*, 3(1), 21–51. <https://doi.org/10.5944/educxx1.3.1.403>
- Field, J. (2001). Lifelong education. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 20(1-2), 3-15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638280010008291>
- Flecha, R. (1990). Spanish society and adult education. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 9(2), 99–108. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0260137900090203>

- Francisco Ortí y Figuerola. (1730). *Memorias historicas de la fundacion, y progressos de la insigne Universidad de Valencia* [*Historical memoirs of the foundation, and progress of the illustrious University of Valencia*]. Imprenta de Antonio Marin.
- García Redondo, E. (2017). La educación de adultos en España durante el periodo azul. Del triunfo militar a la Ley General de Educación (LGE) de 1970 [Adult education in Spain during the blue period. From military victory to the 1970 General Education Law (LGE)]. *Historia y Memoria de la Educación*, 0(5), 441–467.
<https://doi.org/10.5944/hme.5.2017.15383>
- Gomes, I. P., & Lucio-Villegas, E. (2009). Recognition of lifelong and lifewide learning within the scope of permanent education: A new pathway towards citizenship? In E. Lucio-Villegas (Ed.), *Citizenship as politics. International perspectives from adult education* (pp. 71–90). Sense Publishers.
- González, J. V. (1935). *Obras completas de Joaquín V. González, Volumen X* [*Complete Works by Joaquín V. González, Vol. X*]. Imprenta Mercatali. Retrieved from Google Books.
- Hake, B. J. (1999). Lifelong learning policies in the European Union: Developments and issues. *Compare: A Journal of Comparative and International Education*, 29(1), 53-69.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/0305792990290105>
- Hake, B. J. (2011). Rewriting the history of adult education: The search for narrative structures. In K. Rubenson (Ed.), *Adult learning and education* (pp. 14–19). Elsevier.

- Hamilton, J. I. G. (2005). Historical reflections on the splendor and decline of Argentina. *Cato Journal*, 25(3), 521–540.
[http://www.cato.org/sites/cato.org/files/serials/f ... 005/11/cj25n3-11.pdf](http://www.cato.org/sites/cato.org/files/serials/f...005/11/cj25n3-11.pdf)
- HathiTrust. (n.d.). *HathiTrust languages*. Retrieved March 01, 2021, from
http://www.hathitrust.org/visualizations_languages
- HathiTrust Collection Committee. (2012). *Recommendations for handling duplicates in HathiTrust* [Discussion Document].
<https://www.hathitrust.org/documents/hathitrust-collections-duplicates-report-201204.pdf>
- Herrero y Espinosa, M. (1885). *José Pedro Varela*. Librería Nacional.
- Hurtado, J. D. G. (2017). “El delincuente de hoy, será el obrero del mañana”. Políticas de la infancia y trabajo: Instituciones, discursos, prácticas en Colombia (1920-1940) [“Today's delinquent will be tomorrow's worker”. Childhood and labor policies: Institutions, discourses, practices in Colombia (1920-1940)]. *Historia y Sociedad*, 32, 285–315.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.15446/hys.n32.55512>.
- Ignatovich, E. (2020). Mapping a pre-global history of lifelong education with Google Books: 1839 – 1959. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02601370.2020.1801868>
- Institute of Tisiology. (1952). Hoja Tisiológica, Vol.12. Retrieved from Google Books.
- Jarvis, P. (2014). From adult education to lifelong learning and beyond. *Comparative Education*, 50(1), 45–57.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/03050068.2013.871832>

- Jobet, J. C. (1957). Valentin Letelier y sus continuadores [Valentin Letelier and his followers]. *Anales de la Universidad de Chile*, 105, 7–26.
- Jones, E. (2010). Google Books as a general research collection. *Library Resources & Technical Services*, 54(2), 77–89.
<https://doi.org/10.5860/lrts.54n2.77>
- Kallen, D. (1996). Lifelong-learning in retrospect. *Vocational Training*, 8/9, 16–22.
https://www.cedefop.europa.eu/files/etv/Upload/Information_resources/Bookshop/130/8-9_en_kallen.pdf
- Krause, C. C. R. (1860). *Ideal de la humanidad para la vida*, con introducción y comentarios por Julián Sanz del Río [Humanity's ideal for life, with introduction and commentary by Julián Sanz del Río]. Imprenta de Manuel Galiano.
- Kronik, J. W. (1981). Leopoldo Alas, Krausism, and the plight of the humanities in Spain. *Modern Language Studies*, 11(3), 3–15. doi:10.2307/3194374
- La educación en España. Bases para una política educativa [*The Education in Spain. Basis for Educational Policy*]. (1969). *Revista Española de Pedagogía*, 27(105), 91–96. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/23762674>
- Letelier, V. (1892). *Filosofía de la Educación* [*Philosophy of Education*]. Imprenta Cervantes.
- Letelier, V. (1957). Teoría de la enseñanza universitaria [Theory of university education]. *Anales de la Universidad de Chile*, 105, 98–124.

- Limón Mendizabal, M. R. (1988). *Educación permanente y educación de adultos en España* [*Permanent education and adult education in Spain*]. Universidad Complutense.
- Lindeman, E. C. (1926). *The meaning of adult education*.
<https://archive.org/stream/meaningofadulthood00lind?ref=ol#page/n5/mode/2up>
- Lissorgues, Y. (1996). *El pensamiento filosófico y religioso de Leopoldo Alas, Clarín (1875-1901)* [*The philosophical and religious thought of Leopoldo Alas, Clarín (1875-1901)*]. GEA.
- Mandal, S. (2019). The rise of lifelong learning and fall of adult education in India. *London Review of Education*, 17(3), 318–330.
<https://doi.org/10.18546/lre.17.3.08>
- Maíllo, A. (1959). Periodización del trabajo escolar. Almanaque y horario [Periodization of school work. Almanac and timetable]. *Revista de Educación*, 35(101), 57–69.
- Manglano, L. M. (1958, 2 August). Educación permanente [Permanent education]. *La Estafeta Literaria*, 140, 11–11.
https://www.ateneodemadrid.com/biblioteca_digital/Estafeta_Literaria/1958_08_02.pdf
- Mayans y Siscar, G. (1760). *Carta al pavorde Calatayud*. Obras Completas, Volumen V.
<https://bivaldi.gva.es/es/corpus/unidad.do?idUnidad=47679&idCorpus=20000>

- Matheson, D., & Matheson, C. (1996). Lifelong learning and lifelong education: A critique. *Research in Post-Compulsory Education*, 1(2), 219–236. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1359674960010207>
- Medina Ferrer, B., Llorent García, V. J., & Llorent Bedmar, V. (2013). Evolución y concepto de la educación permanente en España [Evolution and concept of permanent education in Spain]. *Revista de Ciencias Sociales (RCS)*, 19(3), 511–522. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=4416650>
- Ministry of Agriculture and Commerce. (1959). *Memoria del Ministerio de Agricultura al Congreso Nacional – 1959* [Report of the Ministry of Agriculture to the National Congress - 1959]. Ministerio de Agricultura y Comercio. Retrieved from Google Books.
- Molleda, M. D. G. (1976). *Unamuno "agitador de espíritus" y Giner de los Ríos* [Unamuno "agitador of the spirit" and Giner de los Ríos]. Universidad de Salamanca.
- National Commission on Culture (1945). *Su labor en 1944* [Its work in 1944]. Buenos Aires.
- Nocedal, C. (1859). *Obras publicadas e inéditas de Don Gaspar Melchor de Jovellanos* [Published and unedited works by Don Gaspar Melchor de Jovellanos]. Tomo II. M. Rivadeneyra.
- Paz Fernández, X. B. (1984). *Educación de adultos y educación permanente* [Adult and continuing education]. Humanitas.
- Perón, J. D. (1953). "La organización de la República y del pueblo es la verdadera organización nacional" dijo Perón a los dirigentes del Partido Peronista de la ciudad de Lobos, provincia de Buenos Aires

[“The organization of the Republic and of the people is the true national organization” said Perón to the leaders of the Peronist Party in the city of Lobos, province of Buenos Aires]. Retrieved from Google Books.

Posada, A. (1957). Valentín Letelier. *Anales de la Universidad de Chile*, 105, 27–33.

Prins, A. (1911). Criminalidad y represión [*Criminality and Repression*]. *Revista General de Legislación y Jurisprudencia*, 119, 67–111.

Real orden disponiendo se adopten las medidas que se publican para difundir en España la enseñanza de la lengua y literatura y el conocimiento de la cultura y el arte italianos [Royal order providing for the adoption of the measures published to disseminate in Spain the teaching of Italian language and literature and the knowledge of Italian culture and art]. *Gaceta de Madrid*, 314, 575–575.

Revista de Educación. (1959). Dos notas destacadas de la Conferencia de Instrucción Pública de Ginebra [Two highlights of the Geneva Conference on Public Instruction]. *Revista de Educación*, 32(90), 12–18.

Ruiz, F. F. (1881). *La fundición Argentina: Demanda contra la provincia de Buenos Aires promovida por Don Francisco Carulla* [*Fundición Argentina: Lawsuit against the province of Buenos Aires by Francisco Carulla*]. Imprenta de la Nación Española.

Steele, T. (2010). Enlightened publics: Popular education movements in Europe, their legacy and promise. *Studies in the Education of Adults*, 42(2), 107–123, <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02660830.2010.11661592>

- Somoza, J. (1885). *Jovellanos: Nuevos datos para su biografía* [*Jovellanos: New data for his biography*]. Propaganda Literaria.
- Suchodolski, B. (1979). Lifelong education at the crossroads. In A. J. Cropley (Ed.), *Lifelong education: A stocktaking* (pp. 34–49). UIE.
- Sutton, M., & Griffiths, M. D. (2018). Using date specific searches on Google Books to disconfirm prior origination knowledge claims for particular terms, words, and names. *Social Sciences*, 7(4), 66.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci7040066>
- Špolar, V. A. M., & Holford, J. (2014). Adult learning: From the margins to the mainstream. In M. Milana & J. Holford (Eds.), *Adult education policy and the European Union: Theoretical and methodological perspectives* (pp. 35–52). Sense Publishers.
- Thomas, R. D. (2006). A general inductive approach for analyzing qualitative evaluation data. *American Journal of Evaluation*, 27(2), 237-246.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1098214005283748>
- Tiana Ferrer, A. (1992). *Maestros, misioneros, militantes: La educación de la clase obrera madrileña, 1898-1917* [*Teachers, missionaries, militants: The education of the Madrid working class, 1898-1917*]. CIDE.
- Tubino, F. M. (1878, 7 October). Exposición Universal de París. Aplicación de las bellas artes a la industria [Universal Exposition of Paris. Application of fine arts to industry]. *La Academia*, 4(13), 193–195.
- Tubino, M. R. (1989). Un académico olvidado: Francisco María Tubino, a los cien años de su muerte (1833-1888) [A forgotten academic: Francisco María Tubino, hundred years after his death (1833-1888)]. *Boletín de la Real Academia de Bellas Artes de San Fernando*, 68, 59–102.

- Tuijnman, A., & Boström, A. K. (2002). Changing notions of lifelong education and lifelong learning. *International Review of Education*, 48(1/2), 93–110. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1015601909731>
- Unamuno, M. (1933, 6 December). Cartas al Amigo [Letters to the Friend]. *Ahora*, 5–5.
- Valdes, A. (1795). *Noticia del Real Instituto Asturiano* [News from the Royal Asturian Institute]. Don Francisco Diaz Pedregal.
- Villarino, J. (1867). *Estudios sobre la colonización i emigración Europea a Chile* [A study on colonisation and European emigration to Chile]. Imprenta Nacional.
- Weiss, A. (2016). Examining Massive Digital Libraries (MDLs) and their impact on reference services. *The Reference Librarian*, 57(4), 286–306. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/02763877.2016.1145614>
- Weiss, A., & James, R. (2013). *An examination of Massive Digital Libraries' coverage of Spanish language materials: Issues of multi-lingual accessibility in a decentralized, mass-digitized world*. 2013 International Conference on Culture and Computing, 10–14. <https://doi.org/10.1109/CultureComputing.2013.10>
- Wiley, W. H. (1918). An experimental study of methods in teaching high school chemistry. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 9(4), 181–198. <https://doi.org/10.1037/h0070825>
- Wilson, A. L. (2009). Lifelong learning in the United States. In P. Jarvis (Ed.), *The Routledge International Handbook of Lifelong Learning* (pp. 512–520). Routledge.

Zięba, A., & Mickiewicz, A. (2018). Google Books Ngram Viewer in socio-cultural research. *Research in Language*, 16(3), 357–375.
<https://doi.org/10.2478/rela-2018-0015>

Table 1

Documents by place of publication and timeframe

Place of publication	1700-1799	1800-1899	1900-1959	Total
Spain	2	16	39	57
Latin America	0	13	150	163
Joint publications	0	1	0	1
Rest of the world	0	0	5	5
Total	2	30	194	226